

HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA - INTROSPECTION AND REMEDIATION

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Intellectual wealth is the most relevant growth indicator of a Nation. However, it is not infrequent to see many juveniles flying overseas to pursue higher studies abroad, ensuing mass exodus and irreversible brain drain.

Indian Education: Present Scenario

The modern system of Higher education in India that started from zilch, now embraces 411 State & 49 Central Universities, 126 Deemed Universities, 334 Private Universities, 39,931 Colleges and 10,725 Standalone Institutions. The system hires 1,518,813 teachers to educate 35.7 million students [University World News, 2020].

Notwithstanding such an eclectic scale of higher education, Indian students in reality do not have a passable access to colleges of high academic stature. With 40% of colleges in metropolitan and municipal areas, only 4.3% colleges have strength of ≥ 3000 students. 16.3% of the HEIs have less than 100 enrollments [AISHE, 2019]. Consequently, only 26.3% of the prospective youngsters get themselves enrolled in colleges as against the global average of 36.7% [UNESCO, 2020]. Let us explore the factors behind this dismal fallout of Indian students that one, supposed to be the forerunners of knowledge, have now been labeled as 'a clan of copy-cats'.

In the wake of globalization, we are 'Aping the West' but we barely match their rapidly evolving educational standards and technology. In India, the course curriculum deals with more of theoretical aspects laced with practical ones, merely as a formality to fall in, with the recent times. The topics of theory and practical have not been intertwined like a workbook. A bulk of mundane information like classification, derivation, lifecycles and inherited basics are drilled into the curriculum, without given a single thought of its application, or putting it with the greed of compulsion rather than elimination. Just because something was taught earlier, does not imply that it holds relevance, in the present times. We Indians, extremely, love to idolize history and do not update curriculum on regular basis. More than the add-ons, deletions in curriculum are necessary, alongside.

Even today, most of the Indian colleges lack ICT assisted teaching and learning modules. On a globe, where ICT offers all advanced tools like teleconferencing, e-mail, audio-learning, virtual classes, interactive voice response system, augmented learning, etc., to the budding scholars, our undergraduates are still relying on hard copies of notes or exam-ready booklets for easy scoring. With the outbreak of pandemic, however, we have come across enhanced virtual learning platforms, in the Country.

In India, 90% of our youth spend the best time of their life preparing for competitive exams for which their aptitude and circumstances do not commensurate. I know many students whose parents are tenants, carpenters or small traders. And not only are they proficient in their traditional business, but they have earned name, identity and prosperity from their family business. But due to a social stigma, yearning for a white collared job, or considering one business trivial or superior than the other, the students are coaxed to pursue engineering or medical stream. Seemingly harmless, this decision indirectly mars the efficiency and interest of human brain, which could have excelled elsewhere, out of passion and interest. The father put all his land and capital at stake, to make their children engineers in some way, but now the city does not offer them jobs and the villages are the not 'dream come true' destinations for them. The parents also have nothing left. It would have been better, had they invested their capital in the child's skill development or in enriching their traditional occupation, but two reasons abstained them from doing so - one, lack of knowledge in traditional occupation and second, society's attitude towards that business. What could be more tragic than that those who have skills, they lack knowledge and those who have knowledge, lack sufficient skills? As per CEO & MD of Tech Mahindra, 94% of Indian graduates are not fit for hiring. According to CTO, Aspiring Minds, only 3.84 percent of engineers in the country have the technical, cognitive, and linguistic skills required for software-related jobs in start-ups. Hardly 3 percent of graduates have new-age technological skills such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, data science [Economic Times, 2018].

Optimal Strategies: Sub Optimal Outcome

In due course of time, the University Grants Commission has taken various reformative steps. The Commission prepared a roadmap to introduce CCE by the year 2012 at undergraduate level. But the over-enthusiastic administration implemented the action plan suddenly in a single academic session that too without sensitizing the academic community and the stakeholders. With the introduction of Semester System, Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation was made mandatory. It caters to regular academic growth and rejects the judgment of student's performance based on few periodic tests or through a single paper-pen examination. It further refutes that scoring 100 per cent signifies the student knows everything about the subject and scoring 0 per cent implies the student knows nothing in the area under discussion. It also considers, intra-examiner and inter-examiner inconsistencies to the tune of 10% on the students' performance during a standard paper-pen examination. Apart from this, it considers several other factors like stress, anxiety, well-being of a student, errors in question papers, etc. that also impinge on the performance of a student.

But, do the students really learn skills or just upload themselves with information? Are they truly endowed with talents to acquire proficiency? And do they comprehend whatever they have gathered so that they can make things happen? Though CCE have thrived in achieving the minimum levels of learning at all stages of education yet it could not do really well in attaining mastery in all competencies. Providing grades, instead of marks, could somehow, shrink the intra-examiner and inter-examiner disparity, in assessment, but failed to overcome the anxiety and fear of an examinee.

The system that has reasonably done well, in transforming the conventional class-rooms (black board- chalk-duster culture) into a collaborative-cum-interactive course group at school level,

has turned out to be a futile experiment, at higher level. With this system, students are mostly engaged in projects, assignments and presentations, thereby getting too little time for self-study or for self-evaluation. In a competitive world, where students get their passport to employment, based on competitive exams, grades no longer remain viable. To score more in competitive exams, either students move to a dummy college or carry out their CCE assignments by 'copy-paste method' without bothering for the contents or relevance of material. CCE, instead of making students more participative, expressive and inventive in the concerned subject, has become an instrument to grant liberal marks, to upsurge their overall percentile in the report cards.

Are we grooming them as professionals or are we churning out well informed, suave individuals who replicate work to survive, rendering quality to none? Are we not increasing to the stack of papers and reports?

Ritualization of Best Practices

In view of India's cultural, socio-economic diversities, University Grants Commission issued guidelines to start vocational and skill-based courses but they too succumb to ritualization. It is common to see that institutes of higher education, before the visit of the National Assessment & Accreditation Council (NAAC) Peer Team, randomly start dozens of add-on courses, certificates and professional programs and as soon as the accreditation process is over, the courses are discontinued in the pretext of students' waning interest or lack of sufficient enrolments. This clearly indicates that proper ground work has not been done before the commencement of courses.

Moreover, the academic staff gets busy all the time in collecting documents and fabricating reports for higher grade and they barely get freedom to bring the fruits of hard-core studies and research. How long can we continue to waste the financial resources received from the World Bank or the Education Commission for the purposes that are unlikely to have any far-reaching consequences? The very purpose of upholding and improving the standards of college education, for which NAAC has been formed, gets diluted consequently.

In every Five-Year Plan, the University Grants Commission earmarks huge allocations for promotion of high-class research. However, most of the students and teachers do not undertake research. The research work is frequently repetitious and restricted as mere fulfillment of requirements to the award of a research degree. Research Papers churned out of such studies contain very little, or at times, no potential information with minor impact factor. If we look back critically, in a population of India, how many Nobel Laureates have been produced by the Country for last 73 years of freedom?

The state of Faculty Training Programs is strictly analogous. Such programs fail to divulge new skills or proficiency as per contemporary needs; rather expert lectures are conducted which scarcely benefit the teaching fraternity. In fact, the quality of college education in India, barring a handful of institutions, is suboptimal as equated to the average world, which is evident with the Academic Ranking of World Universities, Times Higher Education World University Ranking or similar other frameworks [Times, 2020].

In order to achieve higher Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER), efforts were geared up to amass

private spending through Private Public Partnership (PPP). But majority of these colleges, in the quest for profit, began Machiavellian practices like high capitation fee, deception in courses, malpractices in admissions & internal examinations. They tricked the gullible adolescents who were looking for a better course choice at affordable outlays.

In India, the collegiate education system is amazingly stringent and averse to change. Normally, trials or suggestions are never initiated from within the system; when introduced from outside, they are resisted; if imposed, they are ritualized. The aftermath of such innovations like introduction of Semester System, Vocational Courses, Orientation Program (OP), Refresher Courses (RC), College Development Council (CDC), Faculty Improvement Program (FIP), Career Advancement Scheme (CAS) and Performance Based Appraisal System (PBAS) is well-known.

What needs to be worked out at the Higher Education level?

We all know, when buying goods from a sale, we decide what to buy or what not, we choose the item, but do we allow our student to do so - what the student has to study, when to study, how to study and how much to study? Everything is pre-determined by the Board of Studies. Perhaps this is the reason that despite paying full fees, the student does not turn up to college.

For centuries together, there has been a common practice to teach students in masses through lectures, demonstrations, or class-room discussions. It is like, '**One size fit all**' principle that applies to everyone without assessing the customized need of the individual.

Teachers often find it difficult to have an amalgam of activities that create an interest among advanced learners without mislaying the slower ones. However, most of the teachers take a middle path, disappointing the fast learners and puzzling the slower ones. As a long term consequence, there is a dearth of passion and liveliness in the real portals of higher education. Teaching is done but how much is learning generated, is never a point of concern.

In a broader perspective, the prime objectives of higher education, was to help students in:

- acquisition of decent grades in examination;
- construction of knowledge through higher studies and research;
- procurement of gainful employment;
- enhancement of prospects in career; and
- application of acquired knowledge in real life situations.

Despite all efforts, it has never been feasible to achieve all the above goals but for the first one. That is the reason why students are seldom interested in class-room activities.

Role of Faculty and Administration

The academic fraternity needs to realize this fact that brain does not store items like a file cabinet. Therefore, coaxing a student to listen passively and remember disconnected facts cannot stimulate in him, the natural process of learning. In order to induce natural development of brain, there is an urgent need to transform dull and mind-numbing lecture theatres into an enriched learner-friendly environment, where the students may develop new connections with the world around them, in a receptive, but nevertheless relaxed, state of mind. These

connections could be developed at:

- biological level - between neurons, which grow faster with new practices;
- mental level - between concepts, which get validated with new ideas, actions and occurrences; and
- social level - between people, which enhances the pool of knowledge when different people share their viewpoints.

To survive in a globally competitive world, students need creativity, problem solving ability, passion for learning, dedicated work ethic and unquenchable thirst for knowledge. These traits can be inculcated effectively through interactive and participatory methods, wherein the faculty may adopt the curriculum in different ways to cater to the needs of each student in the class. The content taught, the process used and the product expected may also be personalized to help individual student to learn and achieve. Thus, teachers ought to step-off stage and allow learners to take ownership of their own learning, identify topics, develop questions, plan inquiry, divide tasks, generate information and share the learning process. Their wisdom has to be generated as a byproduct of right education.

Apart from these activities, traditional monotonous lectures may be augmented with videos available on virtual platforms. Faculty and students can make use of smart classes for multi-media activities. They can also be shown documentaries and films on science or literature during zero hours. This would permit advanced learners to move at 200% pace while the slow learners may have pause and rewind options. Students' learning propensity can further be speeded up by extending online access to open resources such as DELNET, INFLIBNET, N-list etc.

To ensure effective implementation of learning activities, the Internal Quality Assurance Cells should develop an Institutional Strategic Plan and determine the criteria for assessment of each activity with expected outcome. The productivity of such activities may be gauged on the basis of students' sensitization, involvement, reflection and outcome. The faculty can also take collective feedback to customize the learning process, materials and instructions consistent with the students' need.

Let the Learners take Ownership

The Quality Assurance Cells can also venture upon metacognitive strategies. The students should be granted opportunities to plan organize and monitor their own learning, in order to instill a sense that they are nurturing their own brain-child. It is fast-paced, exciting and personally engaging because students get adequate time & space to become aware of their own level of knowledge and understanding. Further, it promises ample opportunities for individual acceleration and remediation too.

As a best practice, students may be asked to frame questions, prepare answer keys & model answers and evaluate their own answer sheets. Teachers may cross-check their work and make corrections wherever needed. Such practice would empower learners to enjoy ownership of their learning and help them learn from their own mistakes. While this practice seems strange to many teachers, I would mention an instance of sports. Athletes do not spend much time, listening to lectures as how to play their sport? Instead, they practice specific skills,

commit mistakes and work upon their follies. This is how students can be made proficient in higher order thinking like analysis, evaluation, and further correction.

Once the first formative assessment is over and the corrections have been recommended, the students may be provided with parallel formative assessment that addresses the same learning objective with different approach, questions, or prompts. This would verify whether the corrective measures could help the learners to overcome their learning barrier or not. It must well be ensured that the following parameters form the basis of assessment:

- Overall improvement in students' competence - learning, creativity and involvement;
- Identification of areas where learning has happened and where skills have been acquired;
- Demarcation of the areas where students have done fairly well and where improvement is required, viz.
 - ✓ Conceptual clarity;
 - ✓ Description, discussion & illustration;
 - ✓ Qualitative and numerical analysis;
 - ✓ Application of logic or reasoning; and
 - ✓ High order thinking
- Make sure whether the Learning outcomes have been really met with:

After thorough consideration of periodic assessment of students and the report submitted by the faculty, the IQAC can decide whether to continue with the practice or change the chosen strategy. These practices, if effectively directed, would organize learning, synthesize knowledge, and make reflections in personal lives.

References

- Academic Ranking of World Universities, 2019.
- All India Survey In Higher Education, 2019.
- Economic Times, 2018-06-04.
- Education Today, 2019.
- Times Higher Education World Universities Ranking, 2020.
- University World News, 2019.